

Disease brief_HPAI

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>Highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) or 'fowl plague', is a systemic and multi-organ disease of birds.</p> <p>It is caused by (a) an influenza A virus of H5 and H7 subtypes or any influenza A virus with an intravenous pathogenicity index (IVPI) greater than 1,2; or (b) an influenza A virus of H5 and H7 subtypes with a sequence of multiple basic amino acids present at the cleavage site of the haemagglutinin molecule (HA0) that is similar to that observed for other HPAI isolates.</p> <p>Human infections with avian influenza A viruses are uncommon but have occurred sporadically in many countries, usually after unprotected exposures to infected poultry or virus-contaminated environments and have resulted in mild-to-severe illness with a wide range of symptoms and complications. A small number of human infections with avian influenza A viruses have been attributed to exposure to infected wild birds. (1)</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	<p>WOAH: HPAI is a WOAHP-notifiable disease</p> <p>EU: HPAI is a category A disease and listed in Regulation (EU) 2016/429, Reg (EU) 2018/1882, Reg (EU) 2020/2002, Regulation (EU) 2020/689, Reg (EU) 2020/687</p> <p>Co-financed programmes: Yes</p> <p>EU Member States carry put compulsory surveillance programmes for early detection of HPAIV in poultry and wild birds, for detection of HPAIV in poultry species which generally do not show clinical signs or for detecting low pathogenic avian influenza virus which have the potential to mutate to HPAIV. The surveillance must be implemented in both domestic and wild birds in the entire territories of the MSs. Results must be submitted every year via ADIS.</p> <p>Co-financed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Serological surveys to detect H5 and H7 AIV subtype in poultry and follow-up testing of positive serology results by polymerase chain reaction (PCR). <p>Risk-based surveillance to detect HPAIVs in wild birds found dead or moribund by PCR. Birds trapped, hunted or sentinel birds at priority locations and key sites may be also included in the surveillance plan.</p>

3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	From the 2021-2022 epidemics thousands of HPAI H5N1V outbreaks have been recorded in wildlife and poultry globally, 56% in North America and 34% in Europe. The geographical distribution in Europe is updated quarterly.
4	Reservoir / main host	For Influenza A viruses, aquatic migratory birds, mostly in the orders of Anseriformes and Charadriiformes, are regarded as the main reservoir.
5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	<p>HPAIV has an unusually broad host range.</p> <p>Avian species: severe disease and death in poultry: chicken, turkey, quail, guinea fowl, domestic duck, domestic goose and in wild birds, and pet/zoo birds. HPAIV H5N1 has a wide avian host range and infects species rarely found infected with LPAIV, particularly birds not associated with aquatic habitats, such as corvids, birds of prey. The current circulating HPAI H5N1V caused massive mortalities in seabirds, aquatic birds, and raptors.</p> <p>Humans and other mammals: all HPAI H5Nx strains have zoonotic risks but low number of human infections and mild symptoms are reported in the current outbreaks. HPAI H5N1 clade 2.3.4.4b in Europe in the 2021-2022 outbreak affected mammals of the following families/sp: Canidae (red foxes), Mustelidae (European badger, European polecat, ferret), Felidae (<i>Lynx</i>), Suidae (domestic pig), Phocoenidae (porpoise), Phocidae (grey seal, harbour seal).</p>
6	Vector-borne transmission	No.
7	Environmental transmission	<p>Feed and water contaminated by faeces and secretions from infected birds. Infected carcasses of wild birds also contaminate water/environment. AI viruses are resistant and can remain viable for long periods at low temperatures, can also spread between farms via contaminated farm equipment.</p> <p>Among wild animals also transmission through predation and ingestion of infected bird carcasses.</p>
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	Wild birds/faeces from wild birds are considered to be the main source of introduction into poultry establishments. Other sources are via the introduction of infected poultry or contaminated fomites into the farm, or via airborne transmission in areas with high density of poultry farms.
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	Mostly from infected birds, risk for personnel working in infected poultry farms, for example during culling operations. Human infections due to avian influenza

		virus are rare but infections with have been reported in Asia, Africa, Americas and Europe. Detections of avian influenza viruses in humans are updated quarterly.
10	Disease indicators	
11	a) Clinical signs	HPAI in fully susceptible birds: sudden death or development of clinical signs including respiratory signs, nasal and ocular discharges, swelling of the sinuses or head, coughing, snicking, dyspnoea, apathy, reduced vocalisation, marked reduction in feed and water intake, cyanosis, signs of nervous disturbance and incoordination, diarrhoea. Also drop in water/food intake, egg production and reduced egg quality. High morbidity followed by high and rapidly augmenting mortality. None of the signs are specific for HPAI and their expression depends on the species and age of bird, environmental factors and the causative viral strain.
12	b) Seroconversion	Positive birds may have no time to seroconvert given the rapid onset of HPAI general infection, which often leads to sudden death. Most birds seroconvert within 10 days post-inoculation in experimental infections. The accumulation of acquired immunity with age is hypothesized to affect how influenza viruses emerge and spread in species of different lifespans, suggesting long-term immune memory. Experimental work suggests that waterfowl previously exposed to an LPAI virus are more protected against the effects of subsequent exposure with HPAI.
13	c) Other disease indicators	<p>Incubation period in poultry: 1 to 7 days for an individual animal and up to 21 days for a flock. Chicken and turkey are most susceptible, mortality rates can reach 90–100% in 2–12 days after the first clinical signs.</p> <p>Necropsy findings in avian species include haemorrhages and necrosis of the respiratory and gastro-intestinal organs but even severe necrosis and inflammation in multiple organs may not be detected macroscopically. HPAIV has a wide tissue tropism in wild birds and dissemination of the virus differs among species, from localized respiratory tract infection to multiple-organ infection, beyond the respiratory tract the virus has strongest tropism for the central nervous system in many species. Encephalitis is also reported in wild mammals.</p>

14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	<p>HPAI infections should be included in the differential diagnosis of any unexplained mortality of wild birds, in particular when the birds show neurological signs.</p> <p>Domestic birds: rapid spread causing severe disease and death, high mortality, seroconversion has limited value in this case.</p> <p>Wild birds: clinical signs, mortality, and seroconversion. Unusual mortality in wild birds in wetlands during winter is relevant for surveillance based on testing dead animals. Recently, unusual outbreaks occurred during summer.</p>
15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	<p>Diagnostic samples: oropharyngeal and cloacal/faecal swabs, tissue samples from dead animals. Blood/serum samples for serology.</p> <p>DETECTION OF VIRUS: RT-PCR: direct RT-PCR using nucleoprotein-specific or matrix-specific conserved primers applied to diagnostic samples (swabs, organs). In positive samples the presence of the sub-type H5 or H7 influenza virus can be confirmed by using specific primers. Viral isolation in embryonated eggs is used as the reference standard, presence of virus detected by RT-PCR, agar gel immunodiffusion (AGID), ELISAs, or other immunoassays. To differentiate between LPAI and HPAI viruses, virulence tests (Intravenous Pathogenicity Index, IVPI) or genetic tests to detect patterns in the haemagglutinin (HA) can be applied. Antigen test can produce results in 15 min, however, the present recommendation by the WOAHA is that it should only be used to interpret the presence of influenza A at flock level but not for diagnosis in individual birds.</p> <p>SEROLOGICAL TESTS: Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) for serological screening, they detect specific antibodies to a viral nucleoprotein (NP) which has a common antigenicity for influenza A viruses. Hemagglutinin-inhibition (HI) and viral-neutralizing (VN) tests can be used primarily or as additional test to determine the HA subtypes of the viruses. A multi-HA-ELISA can be used as another test for serological surveys of influenza viruses in animals, since it does not require host-specific secondary antibodies, it could potentially be applied for serosurveillance of wild mammals.</p>

16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<p>No surveillance component has been specifically designed, as measures already covered under AHL and USP provide flexibility to MS to include several components already – if such surveillance is to be undertaken under the OH grant, it should not duplicate actions already carried out under AHL and USP.</p> <p>However, it is recommended to carry out WGS of selected strains found in animals, humans and the ecosystem and to integrate the findings in a joint assessment under the One Health approach.</p>																																																				
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="8"></th> <th>Component name</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th>GENERAL POPULATION</th> <th>EXPOSED</th> <th>INFECTED</th> <th>INFECTIOUS</th> <th>SYMPTOMATIC</th> <th>GP/VD VISIT</th> <th>DEAD</th> <th></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td colspan="9" style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white;">Non vector-borne diseases</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="3" style="text-align: center; vertical-align: middle;">HPAI</td> <td style="background-color: #d9e1f2;">Poultry</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">No surveillance component specifically designed, as already covered under AHL and Union Surveillance programmes</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d9ead3;">Wildlife (wild birds and mammals)</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">No surveillance component specifically designed, as measures already covered under AHL and USP provide flexibility to MS to include several components already – if such surveillance is to be undertaken under the OH grant, it should not duplicate actions already carried out under AHL and USP</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #fce4d6;">Human</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Surveillance components targetting human were not in scope</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>											Component name		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/VD VISIT	DEAD		Non vector-borne diseases									HPAI	Poultry							No surveillance component specifically designed, as already covered under AHL and Union Surveillance programmes	Wildlife (wild birds and mammals)							No surveillance component specifically designed, as measures already covered under AHL and USP provide flexibility to MS to include several components already – if such surveillance is to be undertaken under the OH grant, it should not duplicate actions already carried out under AHL and USP	Human							Surveillance components targetting human were not in scope
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17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	Not applicable.																																																				
18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom.																																																				

19	References	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1) https://www.cdc.gov/flu/avianflu/reported-human-infections.htm2) Avian Influenza and Wildlife: Risk management for people working with wild birds3) Quarterly Reports on Avian Influenza4) EFSA AHAW Panel (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare), 2017. Scientific opinion on avian influenza. 4991. EFSA Journal 2017;15(10):4991. 233 pp. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2017.49915) EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), ECDC (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control), EURL (European Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza), Adlhoch C, Fusaro A, Gonzales JL, Kuiken T, Marangon S, Niqueux É, Staubach C, Terregino C, Aznar I, Muñoz Guajardo I and Baldinelli F, 2023. Scientific report: Avian influenza overview September–December 2022. EFSA Journal 2023;21(1):7786, 63 pp.6) Hill SC, Manvell RJ, Schulenburg B, Shell W, Wikramaratna PS, Perrins C, Sheldon BC, Brown IH, Pybus OG. 2016 Antibody responses to avian influenza viruses in wild birds broaden with age. Proc. R. Soc. B 283: 20162159.7) Imai M, Watanabe T, Kiso M, Nakajima N, Yamayoshi S, Iwatsuki-Horimoto K, Hatta M, Yamada S, Ito M, Sakai-Tagawa Y, Shirakura M, Takashita E, Fujisaki S, McBride R, Thompson AJ, Takahashi K, Maemura T, Mitake H, Chiba S, Zhong G, Fan S, Oishi K, Yasuhara A, Takada K, Nakao T, Fukuyama S, Yamashita M, Lopes TJS, Neumann G, Odagiri T, Watanabe S, Shu Y, Paulson JC, Hasegawa H, Kawaoka Y. A Highly Pathogenic Avian H7N9 Influenza Virus Isolated from A Human Is Lethal in Some Ferrets Infected via Respiratory Droplets. Cell Host Microbe. 2017 Nov 8;22(5):615-626.e8.8) Horman WSJ, Nguyen THO, Kedzierska K, Bean AGD and Layton DS (2018) The Drivers of Pathology in Zoonotic Avian Influenza: The Interplay Between Host and Pathogen. Front. Immunol. 9:1812.9) Jianzhong Shi, Xianying Zeng, Pengfei Cui, Cheng Yan & Hualan Chen (2023) Alarming situation of emerging H5 and H7 avian influenza and effective control strategies, Emerging Microbes & Infections, 12:1, 2155072,
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